

ICoRSA Statement on the ERA Act consultation

The European Research Area (ERA) Act represents a key opportunity to address the EU's innovation gap as a structural challenge rather than solely a question of funding levels. While achieving the 3% GDP target for R&D investment is essential, its impact will remain limited unless the ERA Act establishes enforceable measures that strengthen research careers, safeguard academic and scientific freedom, and reduce systemic inequalities across Member States. In this context, ICoRSA, together with its Research Staff member Associations, [ANICT](#), [Max Planck PostdocNet](#) and [NInTec](#), puts forward the following recommendations.

- **Prioritise fundamental and curiosity-driven research**

Increased R&D investment must explicitly safeguard bottom-up, investigator-driven research, which underpins long-term innovation but is increasingly marginalised by short-term, mission-driven funding. Strong, stable public funding at EU and national levels is essential to complement private investment and reduce disparities between research systems.

- **Make job quality a core condition of public R&D investment**

Precarious employment conditions across all sectors and career stages undermine research capacity, talent retention, and innovation outcomes. All publicly funded research positions, including fellowships, must guarantee stable contracts, full employee rights, social protection, and access to career development, in all career stages through a mandatory European Charter for Researchers with effective monitoring and enforcement mechanisms.

- **Establish EU-level protection of scientific and academic freedom**

The ERA Act should set binding minimum standards for scientific and academic freedom by mandating the application of the principles of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) across all EU-funded research projects. Embedding these principles in the ERA Act would ensure that research assessment systems recognise quality, openness, and a broad range of research contributions, including open access publishing and data sharing.

- **Ensure long-term and predictable widening measures**

Policies to reach the 3% GDP target must include sustained widening instruments. Short-term or fragmented approaches risk reinforcing existing disparities. Alignment between EU and national R&I policies should focus on complementarity rather than uniformity, avoiding excessive centralisation that could reduce flexibility and increase administrative burdens.

- **Strengthen transparency, accountability, and legislative coherence of EU research funding**

The European Commission should ensure systematic EU-level data collection on publicly funded research, including funding allocation, beneficiaries, and researchers' employment conditions, supported by harmonised reporting standards across all EU research programmes. Greater coordination and alignment of legislative and regulatory requirements across EU-funded research instruments are essential to ensure transparency, reduce fragmentation, and enable evidence-based policymaking.

- **Strengthen gender equality and non-discrimination within the ERA Act**

Precarious employment conditions and unequal parental leave entitlements drive gender inequality in research and innovation, disproportionately affecting women's career continuity. The ERA Act should translate the objectives of the EU Gender Equality Strategy and the Employment Equality Directive (Directive 2000/78/EC) into concrete measures, ensuring full social rights and equal parental leave for all publicly funded research positions, without discrimination between EU and non-EU researchers.